

STAFF MOTIVATION IN CRISIS SITUATIONS AND MANAGEMENT ACTION TO IMPROVE THE ORGANIZATION'S PERFORMANCE

Author(s)*: Victor-Dumitru MARINIUC
Position: PhD Student
University: "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University of Iași
Address: Iași, Dimitrie Mangeron Str., No. 67, Romania
Email: mariniuc@gmail.com
Webpage: <https://www.tuiasi.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The article examines the relationship between motivation influenced by crisis situations and the improvement of organizational performance under direct involvement of central management.*

Methodology/approach – *Both qualitative and quantitative approaches were employed by means of observation, regarding staff relationships in the unfolding of crisis situations, and by data collection and interpretation of results of the questionnaire applied to the participants of the case study within the organizational context, correspondingly.*

Findings – *Management involvement in the specific manner of direct and unmediated action in the activity of the staff, whose motivation is likely to be influenced in order to ensure favourable conditions for the achievement of the organizational objectives, proved to be effective by improving the expected performance.*

Implications/limitations – *Within organizations, procedures and algorithms are provided for carrying out activities when hypothetical situations arise with the potential to influence the achievement of objectives and affect organizational performance; however, these measures fail to provide an actional model of management in crisis situations generated by armed conflict.*

Value – *This study rises awareness on the importance of enhancing performance of crisis management as regards the cognizance of the psychological profile by categories of staff and of their generic motivation.*

Key words: *crisis management, motivation.*

Introduction

In crisis situations, people are subjected to psychological stress that influences their behaviour in all areas of their activity. Their behaviour within the organizations in which they operate undergoes changes to the extent that their motivation as part of an organizational culture, it either leads them to adopt a positive attitude to participate in the organization to face the crisis or to shelter and save themselves.

Obviously, motivation is in the management's attention, and in order to maintain it with a view to continue to achieve institutional objectives, management must use certain levers of action to exploit its advantage in the direction of improving the performance of the organization.

Crisis changes the working conditions in the organization by creating situational elements that affect the achievement of objectives and performance. Mere staff motivation to overcome the obstacle does not guarantee met objectives and achieved performance. Management levers make the difference in achieving the organization's aim.

Performance represents a superior value achievement compared to the level reached at a given time, under conditions of effectiveness, efficiency and necessity, in the process of fulfilling the pre-set objectives. Conducive to achieving this goal, management seeks the most appropriate ways and means of action and exploits all the opportunities that arise, being permanently interested in maintaining its high level of involvement in the organization.

Organizations respond to such challenges based on the goals pursued in the areas in which they evolve. To this extent, Preda (2006, p.17) considered that “any organization is a rational, institutionalized form of interaction of a group of people, justified by the interest (or pretext) of achieving a common goal.” Correspondingly, Talbot (2019, p.2) claims that public organisations (with reference to departments and ministries, units, programs, systems, etc.) “sit at the intersection of the interest in organizational effectiveness and performance generically and interest in the performance of the public sphere as a whole”.

Crisis is a state of tension that affects parts of or the entire society, with repercussions in all areas of activity. These states involve a great psychological burden that affects the routine of the individuals' lives in all areas of their existence.

What drives people to achieve their aspirations, to overcome the obstacles that get in their way?

Inner stimulation, ambition, and spirit of competition lead individuals to act in the direction mentioned above. This takes on a sense of motivation. Moreover, Indahingwati et al. (2019, p.25-34) state that motivation is the power that enables one to act towards a particular goal.

Could individual motivation ensure performance achievement?

Organizational performance involves achieving a high value threshold in terms of the level of objectives achieved, but this involves a corresponding management of the organization. Individual motivation has an influence on facilitating performance, although it is not a determining factor. Accordingly, Kreitner et al. (1999, p.123-137) argue that although motivation is a necessary contribution to job performance, it is not exclusive. Along with this, a level of skills, knowledge of how to complete tasks, feelings and emotions, conditions of inhibition or facilitation that are not under one's control, etc. are also required.

The **state of armed conflict**, the crisis with the highest degree of tension, affects motivation to such an extent that the individual becomes part of the organization that ensured through organizational culture, the satisfaction of ambition, inner stimulus, the fulfilment of an aspiration, of a self-achievement.

By affecting the smooth development of the activities, the situations created by the crisis lead to the hindrance to the achievement of the objectives under related conditions, and implicitly, to the achievement of the organizational performance. The level of performance is given by the conditions that allow it to be achieved. Basically, management tend to improve the level of performance allowed by difficult conditions, so that it reaches the predictable level achieved under normal conditions. This can be defined as **improving performance**.

Case study. Context

The launch of the military aggression by Russia had as immediate impact the migration of an impressive number of people, mostly Ukrainian citizens, from Ukraine to the EU Member States, the most affected countries being Poland, Hungary, Romania and Slovakia. Most refugees used the *visa free* regime to enter and move within the EU, with very few applying for a form of international protection in the first-entry States. The adoption of Council Implementing Decision (2022) of the EU Council which acknowledges a massive flow of displaced persons from Ukraine within the meaning of Article 5 of Directive 2001/55/EC with the effect of introducing temporary protection created the premises for balancing efforts between Member States, ensuring the Ukrainian citizens the rights of residence and work for at least 1 year.

This specific context led to the involvement of border guards on the eastern border of the European Union in an unprecedented way.

The sudden increase in traffic values, the multitude of atypical procedural situations, exposure to the human drama of refugees, the shortage of resources and personnel are just some of the difficulties faced by border guards at border crossing points. Even though, the border police ensured the successful management of the challenges corresponding to this period as the institution's management made use of action levers that led to the exemplary mobilization of the law enforcement forces.

Research design

This study reproduces the structure of post-action analysis sessions, designed specifically for the specific environment, which answer questions such as:

- a) What were the expected outcomes?
- b) What outcomes could actually be achieved?
- c) What facilitated the achievement of outcomes?

Psychological (motivational) mechanisms were investigated, but also institutional levers used in crisis management. The sample of participants consisted of 46 employees: 84.8 percent men, 15.2 percent women; 45.7 percent of them were in management/coordinating positions; 54.3 percent were professionals in execution positions (21 officers and 25 agents). All (100 percent) carried out their activity in sectors with border crossing points, located on the border with the Republic of Moldova (which were characterised by increased pressure from the perspective of traffic values).

All the management factors within these structures (head and deputy structures, head of border crossing point and five or six employees in executive positions (appointed by statistical step of five), were selected to participate in the study, known as distinct for their involvement and the outcomes in the activity carried out in the entire period since the beginning of the armed conflict in Ukraine.

Research results and data interpretation

The main interest of the study is identifying the main difficulty that a border crossing points employees faced in the context of the armed conflict in Ukraine. As shown by the analysis of the results presented in the table below, the difficulties reported of by the respondents referred mainly to **the atypical nature of the situations encountered, their unique character** (43,5 percent), **doubled by the pressure exerted by high traffic values** (34,8 percent).

Table 1. The main difficulty encountered in my professional activity at the border crossing point during the last month

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	high traffic values	16	34,8	35,6	35,6
	the multitude of unregulated situations / incidents / that exceed work procedures	20	43,5	44,4	80,0
	the presence of persons not directly related to border police work at the border crossing points	1	2,2	2,2	82,2
	lack of resources (material, human) necessary to carry out the activity	4	8,7	8,9	91,1
	situations that affected me emotionally	4	8,7	8,9	100,0
	Total	45	97,8	100,0	
Missing	System	1	2,2		
Total		46	100,0		

The study is meant to identify aspects the employees considered helpful in dealing with the consequences of the Ukrainian crisis. The right dissemination of their performances makes it possible to replicate a successful actional model in similar situations or to substantiate some approaches to optimize problematic or dysfunctional aspects.

Professional training of employees (M=2,58) was ranked on the first place among the resources mentioned by the border crossing points staff, followed by **the support provided by the superiors** (with reference to the central management from the organization's headquarters), stress resistance, the support offered by colleagues, family support, physical resistance. On the last place is the previous

experience in crisis management and the resources (human, logistical, time) on which they could rely in performing specific tasks.

The *T-test for independent samples* revealed statistically significant differences between management positions and execution positions in relation to the support received from their superiors (in the sense that respondents in management positions evaluate the support received from the management as being more consistent in relation to those in executive positions, $t=-2.05$, $DF=43.41$, $p\leq 0.05$, which indicates that, at least at the level of subjective perception, middle management has received more organizational support than it provided).

There are also statistically significant differences in the sense that superiors believe that physical resistance helped them more during this period compared to their subordinates ($t=2.37$, $DF=42.63$, $p\leq 0.05$), whereas the latter perceived support from the family as stronger than that felt by their superiors ($t=-1.94$, $DF=35.56$, $p\leq 0.05$).

The research design is based on the hypothesis that the results obtained by employees should not be motivated by obtaining rewards or avoiding punishments, but by factors associated with intrinsic motivation, a concept discovered by researchers in the mid-20th century. According to Pink (2011, p.149) three main elements favour people's involvement in action: "autonomy, the desire to direct our own lives; mastery, the urge to get better and better at something that matters; and purpose, the yearning to do what we do in the service of something larger than ourselves."

Encouraging professional performance by stimulating intrinsic motivation is based on autonomy, in terms of tasks (what I do), time (when I do), team (with whom I do) and method (how I do). In highly hierarchical structures such as those of safety and public order, including the institution, one could only discuss autonomy in relation to the way specific tasks are performed (the team, the time and the type of task are not under the employees' control). An amount of 80.5 percent of the study participants stated that they were able to organize their own way of performing tasks to a large and very large extent during the armed conflict in Ukraine.

Figure 1. I consider that after this period, I was able to organize my own way of carrying out tasks.

Mastery involves, according to Pink (2011, p.233), exposure to challenges adapted to one's own abilities, which are "infinitely improvable, [...] involving effort, grit and deliberate practice" (158). For this reason, 83,1 percent of the employees surveyed believe that their professional experience helped them to become better.

Last but not least, the feeling of serving an objective superior to individual interests is present in 65.2 percent of respondents' answers. In the case of the crisis in Ukraine, the purpose of the work of border crossing point staff was an implicit one, immediately understood and having both professional and humanitarian character ("We are here and we are doing everything in our power to help these people

run away from the path of war", "We put all our knowledge into practice to prevent those who take advantage of the context of war to commit illegal acts".

Figure 2. I am a better border guard.

Figure 3. I feel that my work serves an objective superior to my personal interests.

Modulation of intrinsic motivational factors was achieved by implementing measures aimed at creating a sense of belonging, connection and safety at the group level.

To this end, **the superiors consulted their subordinates in decision-making, worked side-by-side, providing a personal example** (78.2 percent believe that this happened to a large and very large extent), **showed their availability to answer questions, in a non-normed schedule** (80.4 percent), **asked for and provided constructive feedback**, and errors were evaluated as contexts for learning and development.

There is therefore a positive polarization of all attitudes that increase motivation for involvement in the activity. These behaviours made it possible to agglutinate work teams and strengthen the belief that "We are close, we are safe, we share a future". (Coyle, 2018, p.45)

Figure 4. My superiors worked with me side-by-side, providing a personal example.

Figure 5. I feel that I have someone to learn new things from, I have people around who inspire me.

Figure 6. The managers were available to help me in making decisions, including out of working hours.

Figure 7. I received positive feedback.

Figure 8. My superiors made me feel that my work is appreciated and valued.

Conclusions

The research material provides with an answer in terms of the necessary strength that stimulates the organization's activity in a crisis situation. Managers need to be fully aware of the elements of organizational culture crisis (slogans, logos, principles) in order to be able to activate them intensively in crisis situations.

An essential thing to ensure the success of organizational objectives was knowledge, training and skills trained by staff, which should be a permanent priority for management. The most obvious factor that represented a strong lever in stimulating activity in crisis situations was management support.

What did that consist of?

It consisted of direct participation within the organization, achieving direct communication between the top of the hierarchy and the basic level on which the achievement of organizational objectives directly depended. Another aspect was the specific qualification for such situations so that management not only had the role of directing and supervision but also was directly involved, where appropriate and cogent among the basic level, in working teams, identifying together solutions to overcome obstacles and optimize the activity.

The staff inner motivation was strengthened through physical presence, by direct taking over of the newly emerging problems by the central management, and also through organizational culture elements such as: "we are here on the front line", "this is what we trained for". Thus, they succeeded to fulfil the organization's objective of maintaining constant and continuous border surveillance and control.

In conclusion, in order to achieve the success of the improvement of organizational performance, management must be directly involved within the organization's mechanism and directly tackle the problems arising in specific crisis situations. In future crisis situations, management will have to consider the need for its mobility at all levels of the organization and ensure direct and unmediated communication with the personnel involved in ensuring the achievement of the organizational objective. Furthermore, it would be appropriate for the members of the central management to take on the role of specialists in specific fields, by creating a sense of trust of the staff led in the institutional capacity to overcome obstacles.

References

Coyle, D.

2018

The Culture Code: The Secrets of Highly Successful Groups: 45. Bantam.

Indahingwati, A., Launtu, A., Tamsah, H., Firman, A., Putra, A., & Aswari, A.

2019

"How Digital Technology Driven Millennial Consumer Behaviour in Indonesia". Journal of Distribution Science 17-(8): 25-34.

Kreitner, R., Kinichi, A., & Buelens, M.

1999

Organizational Behaviour:123-137. (F. E. Higher Education, Ed.) McGraw-Hill.

Pink, D.

2011

Drive: The Surprising Truth about What Motivates Us: 231-(3). Riverhead Books.

Preda, M.

2006

Comportament organizațional. Teorii, exerciții, studiu de caz: 17. Iași: Polirom.

Talbot, C.

2010

Theories of Performance. Organizational and Service Improvement in the Public Domain: 2. New York: Oxford University Press.